

THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AS A MEDIATING VARIABLE BETWEEN TALENT MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES AND DIGITAL PERFORMANCE IMPROVEMENT

SAMI AWWAD AL-KHARABSHEH

Business Administration Department, Faculty of Business, Amman Arab University, Amman-Jordan.

Abstract

Successful organizational operations in the competitive business world depend heavily on efficient Talent management. Employee turnover is increasing because traditional methods of developing and retaining talent frequently fall short of addressing the complexity of contemporary workforce dynamics. The main objective was to assess how artificial intelligence (AI) influences the relationship between TM and digital performance enhancement in Jordanian ICT companies. To gather the relevant data this study used a quantitative approach. The statistical population of the research comprised 180 senior managers from ICT companies in Jordan. The relevant information was gathered through the use of a standard questionnaire. To analyze the obtained model, Smart PLS version 4.07 software was used. The results showed that the incorporation of AI in TM strategies enhances the firm's DP. This study adds to our understanding of the TM future, which is improved by AI to help businesses succeed and adapt in the digital age.

Keywords: Talent Management (TM), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Talent Analytics (TA), Talent Acquisition (TAC), Succession Planning (SP), Performance Management (PM), Digital Performance (DP).

INTRODUCTION

Businesses and manufacturers are dealing with technological advances more than ever before. The gig economic activity, digital transformation, digitalization, and the rise of Industry 4.0 and 5.0 are becoming essential for companies. Ideas like this suggest a change in every facet of the workplace. Since the workplace is changing and demands new competencies and abilities, TM must be focused on managing proficiency and expertise. TM refers to the systematic, end-to-end procedures for selecting, recruiting, and assisting the best personnel while considering organizational goals. Digital transformation involves people and culture more than technology. While technology may be purchased, acquiring a digital future requires learning new skills, minimizing the distance between the availability and demand of talent, and preparing the talent for its full potential (Frankiewicz 2020). To achieve strategic, long-term organizational success, TM refers to the procedures and activities that entail the deliberate recruitment, verification, improvement, participation, maintenance, and placement of those talents that are especially valuable to an organization (Abid, 2024). As a result, human resources particularly those with extensive understanding and expertise, the ability to gain knowledge and grow continuously, the ability to quickly adapt and create new technologies, and the production in businesses is mostly driven by employees' ability to interact and share information. There is fierce rivalry among contemporary businesses in recruiting and retaining talents and workers with high knowledge and skills (Marin, 2023).

Organizations compete for a diverse workforce and market shares in this digital transformation era. Additionally, candidates seek a work environment that values individuals as assets instead of as automated robots and fosters talent development. Talent management recognizes that an organization's people are its real power. It has become crucial to bring in, educate, and keep top people as technology developments transform sectors and employment positions (Pereira et al, 2022). Lack of talent compels businesses or organizations to struggle for the same individuals to efficiently maintain, expand, and fulfill the company's objectives. Successful personnel management is one of the most critical criteria for firms seeking to build a continuous competitive advantage.

Long-term organizational success, improving digital performance, and accomplishing goals and objectives are all made more likely by the successful and productive handling of human resources. Talented employees are the primary resources resulting in long-term competitive advantages and outstanding digital performance. Gallardo et al (2020) suggested that every organization's development and digital success rely on having the appropriate people with the appropriate competencies in the perfect locations at the proper times. Companies utilize talent management as a method to maximize their hiring, training, and retention of employees. Using talent management, employers may enhance employee satisfaction, top talent retention, financial goal achievement, staff productivity, and creativity. Businesses may improve digital performance and extend the employment lifetime by focusing on talent development and utilization (Samoilenko, 2023).

To be competitive, businesses in all sectors must constantly find ways to bring in, keep, and nurture great people. In addition to putting the appropriate people in the right positions, effective TM strategies can improve employee engagement, create a great company culture, and boost overall performance. Yet, manual procedures and a lack of data-driven insights are characteristics of old HR strategies, which are increasingly failing to meet the expectations of the modern workforce (Faqih and Miah,2023). AI is transforming TM by providing new techniques and approaches to mechanize, improve, and customize a range of procedures. Organizations may move from reactive to proactive TM strategies because of AI's ability to recognize patterns, analyze huge quantities of statistics, and forecast (Siradhana, 2023). Organizations may improve decision-making, enhance digital performance, obtain a better understanding of employee behavior, and provide more individualized talent development programs that meet the requirements of both individual employees and company objectives by incorporating AI into their HR and TM procedures (Pillai, 2020). AI acts as the mediator between TM strategies and digital performance improvements. AI presents a viable way to address the difficulties associated with contemporary personnel management. AI-powered solutions can forecast turnover risks, evaluate employee data instantaneously, and provide customized actions to increase retention. For example, HR managers might use predictive analytics models to find employees who are likely to leave based on variables like training hours, job satisfaction, and engagement scores. AI may also help with individualized development and learning by putting employees in groups based on shared skills and career objectives and creating training plans that are tailored to every person's prerequisite (Paigude et al ,2023).

Additionally, using feedback data, AI-driven evaluation of sentiment can evaluate employee productivity, allowing businesses to address possible discontent before it results in turnover. In addition to retaining their most important staff, these skills enable businesses to support their professional growth in a manner that supports both individual and corporate goals. Employee engagement, organizational performance, digital performance, and turnover rates might all be considerably decreased with this change in people management techniques (Olaniyan et al,2022).

This study aims to determine how TM affects digital DP in Jordanian ICT (communications and information technology) firms, using AI as the mediating variable, and to investigate how AI influences the connection between TM strategies and the enhancement of DP.

Research questions

- 1) To what extent does AI improve TM strategies' efficiency in enhancing digital performance?
- 2) How can companies boost digital performance by incorporating AI into their TM strategies?

The current research selected talent analytics (TA), talent acquisition (TAC), performance management (PM), and succession planning (SP) as the strategies of TM. Digital performance is measured through social media, data and analytics, and mobile performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

One of the most important procedures that influences organizational results is TM. They have a direct impact on workers' output, which helps businesses maintain their competitiveness. According to current business realities, it is getting harder for businesses to find and retain workers with the necessary abilities. Effective personnel recruiting, growth, and retention support the organization's objectives and strategy. When employees are engaged, they produce more, and businesses that prioritize talent management eventually profit. Accordingly, TM has become essential for development, and employer branding and a deliberate method of TM are becoming critical for keeping top performers (Hongal & Kinange, 2020). The prior method of handling talent is becoming less effective as it is not centered on routine HR tasks. It is currently considered a strategic need. But, as skills are changing, finding the proper talent has become much harder. Outdated techniques cannot capture modern characteristics; instead, creative approaches supported by technology are needed. By offering competitive compensation, encouraging work conditions, and opportunities for professional advancement, employers can concentrate on retaining their staff. The gig economy and the digitization of business are two examples of phenomena that have changed the landscape of TM. Businesses must thus adapt as needed to be competitive in the market (Groenewald et al., 2024).

Companies compete more fiercely in the digital age due to technological advancements that make information easily and rapidly accessible. Businesses need to leverage digital

technologies like social networking sites, the web, handheld gadgets, and cloud-based applications to stay relevant and competitive. Their digital performance is also measured through them. Businesses face the risk of losing clients and market share if they can't adjust to these developments (Vapiwala et al., 2023). In the digital business environment, performance metrics include social media and mobile performance monitoring and real-time data updates. Businesses will have a clear edge if they can use social media and analytical data to comprehend customer behavior, industry trends, and supply chain optimization. Businesses can accurately assess digital performance, make more precise predictions, and make wiser decisions thanks to big data and AI technologies. This makes the digital age a difficult place to compete, but it also presents excellent opportunities for creative and flexible businesses to improve their digital performance (Gupta et al, 2021).

According to Abdelazim (2021) when it comes to enhancing a business's digital performance and competitiveness, talent management is crucial since trained and competent employees are the primary resources that can ignite innovation and growth. In an increasingly competitive corporate world, having a capable and tech-savvy staff may make the difference between winning and losing businesses. Recruitment, training, and development procedures must be conducted with this goal in mind to maximize the potential of the greatest personnel and enable them to contribute to the organization to the fullest extent possible. Investing in TM also helps to boost output and efficiency at work. Employee motivation and work satisfaction increase when they have chances to grow professionally and feel appreciated. Better performance, more innovative thinking, and a solution-oriented strategy result from this, all of which are critical in the face of intense market competition (Mora, 2022). Furthermore, businesses that prioritize employee development typically have greater retention rates, which indicates that they can retain the knowledge and abilities that have been developed within the company.

Due to innovation and technology, TM strategies are now being restructured. Organizations are under pressure to adapt and develop fresh ideas that will set them apart in the modern world. Technology-integrated practices, which take the role of conventional methods, use technology in areas including hiring, performance reviews, and pay. Virtual platforms and social media have become essential for keeping personnel. Thus, the move to digitization is a component of a broader trend where businesses are eager to implement TM best practices that will increase their productivity and competitiveness (Chew et al, 2024).

Effective personnel management is essential to a firm's longstanding sustainability, particularly for businesses involved in the ICT industry. Research indicates that putting employee management strategies into practice leads to improved digital performance and sustainability efforts. As a result, in terms of talent management, businesses may keep attracting, retaining, and offering individuals growth chances in a way that aligns with both their objectives and societal demands. A company's reputation and digital performance may suffer if the management of employees is neglected (Madhur et al., 2024).

Using TM reduces the amount of time needed to find leaders and experts to replace them. Whether via corporate candidates or outside applicants, the primary objective is to meet the need for competent persons at the exact moment when they are needed. According to earlier research, proactive internal succession planning lowers transaction costs, which increases company profit. A smooth succession may also improve the quality of work and lessen knowledge loss since, for instance, practices and information may be passed down directly. This method also improves digital performance since, social media performance, data and analytics, and mobile performance are highly affected by good TM (Taechasapasith,2023). The availability of personnel for new positions and the effective integration of new leaders are clear indicators of the advantages of succession planning. Planning for succession improves financial outcomes and digital performance after succession. According to Damer (2020), the effectiveness of succession planning is correlated with an organization's capacity to implement talent development initiatives to find and train potential leaders. Business executives must define what makes up a workable recruitment and retention framework even if talent development programs might aid in efficient succession planning. The above literature showed that SP is one of the vital strategies of the TM that directly affects the digital performance of the firm. Based on this the study hypothesized:

H1a: TM focusing on succession planning (SP) improves the firm's digital performance.

Another important strategy of TM that can improve the digital achievement of the firm is talent analytics. Data about employees has always been of importance to organizations. Despite the recent emergence of the term "talent analytics," companies have been trying to understand the data they keep about their personnel to enhance performance. The ability of businesses to integrate a variety of data sources, and utilize them to address critical issues regarding recruiting, keeping, and managing HR is especially recent (Kaewnaknaew et al., 2022). One of the most important duties of HR departments is training current personnel (Ochieng, 2023). Analytics-based dashboards have been used to develop a tailored training course for new recruits that takes into consideration their educational background and employment requirements. Dashboards can generate data, which can be utilized to determine the ROI of the training expenditure. To create performance management systems that may award workers according to their performance, firms often gather a significant quantity of data on each employee. To map and relate organizational digital performance to individuals or teams, talent analytics provides the means to tie employee performance management to compensation (Saputra et al, 2022). Companies have utilized talent analytics to find prospective applicant pools in previously ignored jobs. This is particularly crucial in situations when positions need specialized skill sets, and they may be trying to hire from the same group of applicants as their rivals. In either scenario, businesses may use talent analytics to identify applicants from various backgrounds who possess the required skill sets (Thakral et al, 2023). Based on the above literature we can hypothesize:

H1b: TM focusing on talent analytics (TA) improves the firm's digital performance

Long-term survival and competitiveness in the marketplace depend largely on an organization's human and intellectual capital, even amid recent advancements and intense competition in the market (Ghosh, 2021). Successful businesses place a high priority on their human capital. They recognize the necessity for efficient personnel supervision and acquisition tactics to make the most of their talent pool and reduce any additional costs. The prevailing trend that can be seen across the board is the effect of AI adoption on the actual implementation of AI and ML for talent acquisition (Pillai & Sivathanu, 2020). As the world continues to change and corporations deal with the present digitization, they have come to recognize the need to use social networking sites (SNWs) to recruit exceptional people to achieve sustainability and creativity. The recruiting patterns have been given an updated appearance by SNWs (Rehman et al., 2021). With the development of SMART technology, social networking sites have made their way into the workplace and now serve as platforms for recruiting and selecting new employees. They are no longer just means to stay in contact with friends and family (Chang et al., 2022). During this era of digital transformation talent acquisition has become an important factor in the digital performance of the firm. Thus, we can hypothesize:

H1c: Talent management with a focus on talent acquisition (TAC) improves the firm's digital performance

Another important dimension of talent management is PM. Almohtaseb et al. (2020) argue that PM removes the subjectivity from manager-conducted performance evaluations and performance awards. A wide feeling of equity is also fostered via performance management, allowing any employee to receive performance awards by adhering to the company's established standards and objectives. All organizational choices, work activities, and resource allocation should be based on and motivated by an efficient performance management system. When talent management is complemented by performance management, organizational digital performance will improve; when performance management is unrelated to talent management, organizational digital performance may suffer. A well-executed performance management enhances employee-manager communication and helps to raise the standard of work produced by employees. It also makes it easier to comprehend the objectives of the company and work requirements (Aguinis,2021). Employee psychological commitment is also increased via performance management, which also inspires and facilitates a more vibrant workplace culture and improves the digital performance of the firm. Therefore, using the following assumptions, this study investigates the influence of PM on organizational DP, based on the claim that it enhances digital performance.

H1d: TM focusing on performance management improves the firm's digital performance

Talent management is undergoing a revolution because of the introduction of AI, which provides new tools and approaches to automate, optimize, and customize different operations. AI helps businesses transform from reactive to proactive talent management practices by analyzing large volumes of data, finding trends, and making predictions. AI presents a viable answer to contemporary talent management problems (Hector,2023).

AI-powered solutions can forecast turnover risks, evaluate employee data in real-time, and provide customized actions to increase retention. Using variables like engagement levels, job happiness, and training hours, machine learning models, for example, may assist HR managers in identifying workers who are in danger of leaving. AI may also support individualized learning and development by assembling workers with comparable abilities and professional objectives and creating training plans that are tailored to each worker's needs (Faqihi, 2023). Additionally, using feedback data, AI-driven sentiment analysis can evaluate staff morale, allowing businesses to address possible discontent before it results in turnover. In addition to retaining their most important staff, these skills enable businesses to support their professional growth in a manner that supports both individual and corporate goals and improves the overall digital performance of the firm. Employee engagement, organizational digital performance, and turnover rates might all be considerably decreased by this change in people management procedures (Popo et al, 2022). Strategies for developing and retaining people have undergone a paradigm shift since the implementation of AI in HR handling. AI is becoming an important item for businesses looking to increase retention, engagement, and development because of its capacity to automate, expect, and personalize various personnel management activities (Kamaruddin et al, 2023). Based on this literature we hypothesize:

H2: TM strategies significantly affect AI

H3: AI positively affects the digital performance of the fir

H4: The connection between digital performance and TM strategies is mediated by AI.

METHODOLOGY

Research Techniques

The field technique has been employed to gather information about the validation or acceptance of research hypotheses. A survey was employed to gather information in the second phase after the initial phase was completed using resources such as books, scientific journals, and papers published on this subject.

Research Design

This study used a quantitative approach to examine how AI mediates the association between TM strategies and DP improvements.

Research Respondents

The study's statistical population consists of senior managers from ICT companies. For this study's quantitative investigation of the influence of TM on DP improvement with the mediating function of AI, samples of managers and specialists from Jordanian ICT enterprises were selected at random.

Research Instrument

Six of the questionnaire's questions asked about demographics, and the other questions were related to model constructs. To gauge their perspectives, respondents had to select

from the 5 point scale. Respondent confidentiality was maintained throughout the electronic distribution of the questionnaires.

Sample Size

350 questionnaires in all were electronically distributed to senior managers of Jordanian ICT businesses. Only 200 were returned by the respondents. Of the returned questionnaires 20 were incomplete so they were rejected. After that 180 questionnaires were selected for the study.

Data Analysis and Discussion

To assess the constructs' excellence for estimating validity and consistency and examine the associations between various items for hypothesis analysis, the study uses a measurement model and a structural model. Smart PLS version 4.0.7.is used to conduct the test.

Measurement Model

When evaluating an outside model, validity and reliability must be taken into account. All factor loadings in exploratory studies are acceptable when they are greater than 0.5, and the alpha coefficient should be 0.7 or higher. Every variable has an alpha coefficient value greater than 0.7. In the same way, the acceptable CR is more than 0.7 (Cheung et al,2024). This requirement is accepted as all constructions have a CR of 0.7 or above (Table 1). If the AVE value for each construct is more than 0.5, this condition will be satisfied. To support convergent validity, it has been proposed that the value of the CR should be much greater than the AVE (Purwanto, 2021). Every construct's CR value exceeds its AVE value, and each construct's AVE value is above 0.5. The findings indicate that the constructs' reliability and convergent validity have been established.

Table 1: Convergent validity

Constructs	Items	FL	ACC/N.ACC	CR	AVE
Succession Planning	SC1	0.823	Accepted	0.915	0.682
	SC2	0.811	Accepted		
	SC3	0.799	Accepted		
	SC4	0.861	Accepted		
	SC5	0.835	Accepted		
Talent Analytics	TA1	0.897	Accepted	0.912	0.674
	TA2	0.798	Accepted		
	TA3	0.738	Accepted		
	TA4	0.801	Accepted		
	TA5	0.863	Accepted		
Talent Acquisition	TAC1	0.753	Accepted	0.913	0.636
	TAC2	0.798	Accepted		
	TAC3	0.799	Accepted		
	TAC4	0.865	Accepted		
	TAC5	0.732	Accepted		
	TAC6	0.831	Accepted		
Performance Management (PM)	PM1	0.798	Accepted	0.895	0.630

	PM2	0.799	Accepted		
	PM3	0.733	Accepted		
	PM4	0.812	Accepted		
	PM5	0.824	Accepted		
AI	AI1	0.802	Accepted	0.909	0.667
	AI2	0.833	Accepted		
	AI3	0.795	Accepted		
	AI4	0.833	Accepted		
	AI5	0.821	Accepted		
Digital Performance	DP1	0.863	Accepted	0.955	0.678
	DP2	0.821	Accepted		
	DP3	0.798	Accepted		
	DP4	0.761	Accepted		
	DP5	0.841	Accepted		
	DP6	0.87	Accepted		
	DP7	0.799	Accepted		
	DP8	0.827	Accepted		
	DP9	0.857	Accepted		
	DP10	0.789	Accepted		

The discriminant validity was then confirmed using the HTMT ratio of correlation using Smart PLS using the Fornell–Larcker approach; the association between the values of latent variables is compared with the square root of the AVE. This technique required that associations with other latent variables be less than the AVE for each construct.

This investigation has shown that it satisfies this condition. To verify the discriminant validity of the model, every ratio has to be less than 0.9; if the value is around 1, discriminant validity won't be present. Every ratio in the matrix had a value less than 0.9, as Table 2 demonstrates.

Table 2: HTMT Ratio

	SC	TA	TAC	PM	AI	DP
SC						
TA	0.711					
TAC	0.702	0.701				
PM	0.648	0.733	0.692			
AI	0.613	0.691	0.732	0.706		
DP	0.632	0.623	0.701	0.711	0.605	

Structural Model

β (path coefficient) has been used to assess the structural model. Table 3 summarizes the β between the constructs computed by Smart PLS. The path coefficient indicates the link that exists between latent constructs as well as their strength and direction.

Using Smart PLS to analyze the path correlations, the bootstrapping approach was applied. All t-statistics range from 1.933 to 2.981 and values of p are less than 0.05, indicating that all study theories are verified.

#	Research Hypothesis	β	S.Dev	T-stats	P-values	Status
H1a	SP->DP	0.214	0.091	2.417	0.001	Accepted
H1b	TA->DP	0.258	0.121	2.361	0.000	Accepted
H1c	TAC->DP	0.197	0.102	1.933	0.002	Accepted
H1d	PM->DP	0.231	0.091	2.229	0.000	Accepted
H2	TA->AI	0.278	0.051	2.096	0.001	Accepted
H3	AI->DP	0.236	0.069	2.981	0.000	Accepted
H4	TA->AI->DP	0.291	0.072	2.311	0.000	Accepted

The P values of H2, H3, and H4 revealed that all of them are significant which means that AI influences the association between TM and DP as a mediating variable. Hence, this paper elaborated on the positive impact of AI as a mediating variable between TM and DP improvements.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated how well AI performs as a mediator between TM and DP improvements. By transforming the traditional approach of talent management and assisting businesses in enhancing their digital performance, TM strategies including succession planning, talent analytics, talent acquisition, and performance management have become essential in managing HR in the digital age. As companies become more HR-focused, AI is supporting them in creating a more positive work environment, increasing workforce productivity, and creating a pleasant working environment, all of which contribute to increased staff contribution and enhanced DP of the business (Taguimdje et al., 2020). AI integration into TM strategies represents an entirely new approach to the business's operations and might result in increased output, expansion, and improvement of the company's online performance. Businesses can benefit from increased productivity, new business prospects, new approaches to business model creation, new HR management strategies, and encouragement of innovation and development through the usage of AI technology (Wiblen et al, 2021).

In this study, the authors examined how well TM strategies work in digital performance. Hiring the appropriate individuals in a more quantifiable, timely, and digital way was made possible by managers and staff members with the help of AI-integrated TM. Digitalization made it easier for the HR department and other departments like technical, finance, etc., to communicate with one another and clearly understand one another's procedures. Customized services such as learning and employment possibilities, individualized information intelligence, performance monitoring, training, development, etc., can be implemented through digitalized HR management.

LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study's first limitation is the firms that are being examined. This study focused on the senior management of ICT companies in Jordan. Based on the cultural perspectives, attitudes, and other characteristics of the participants in this study, a comparison analysis of other ICT firms in other nations would provide different findings. Therefore, this subject

might be investigated in various businesses, regions, and industrial sectors in future studies.

The second limitation was that the complex questionnaire was unable to display the actual findings. Additionally, respondents may react to questions based on their concerns. Thus, using modern data-gathering techniques like data mining in subsequent studies may produce more accurate results. Additionally, 180 of the 350 copies of the questionnaires that were distributed were analyzed. It seems to reason that more surveys and, hence, the information gathered can improve the output's validity and consistency

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